

Research

Anti-inflammatory Activities of Different Types of Yemeni honey on Rats

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Abstract: This study aimed to evaluate the anti-inflammatory activities of eight different types of Yemeni honey using an acute inflammation rat model. Ten groups were employed in this study ($n=8$ rats for each group), Rats paw edema was induced by sub plantar injection of 1% carrageenan into the right hind paw. Rats were pre-treated with different types of Yemeni honey (Osaimi sider, Athel, Al-Akhawain, Salam, Somar, Majra, Acacia and Algasas) at a dose (5mg/kg b.w) and NSAID as Indomethacin (10 mg/kg, p.o.) for 7 days. The diameter of the hind paw was measured for assessment of the edema size at 1, 2, 4, 6 and 24 hours. The different types of Yemeni honey significant anti-inflammatory efficacies against carrageenan-induced paw edema in rats. Besides, the different types of Yemeni honey, elevate numbers of RBCs, Hb and PCV with a reduction in WBCs numbers. Marked reduction in percentages of neutrophil, lymphocyte and basophils. Moreover, they succeeded to reduce the elevated serum AST level. Algasas honey and osaimi sider honey possesses a better anti-inflammatory activity which was almost similar to the effect of the Indomethacin, followed Dam Al-Akhawain honey (Acacia honey). Where Athel, Salam and Somar honey, their anti-inflammatory activity differed according to the source and the level of honey. Therefore, these discrepancies could be attributed to the differences of botanical sources of honey and also to the presence of different compounds of anti-inflammatory that have different anti-inflammation effects. **Conclusion:** The different types of Yemeni honey (Osaimi sider, Athel, Dam Al-Akhawain, Salam, Somar, Majra, Acacia and Algasas) possess anti-inflammatory activity. Also, they were safe at the doses used.

Keywords: Anti-inflammatory activities; Yemeni honey types; Hematological Assay; Animal experimental Design

Introduction

Honey is a sweet and flavorful natural product of honey bees that is derived from floral nectars and other plant secretions [1]. The major component of honey is a complex mixture of sugars such as glucose, fructose and sucrose with small number of other constituents including minerals, amino acids, proteins, enzymes, organic acids, phenolic compounds and vitamins [2]. Honey is considered as part of traditional medicine. The therapeutic potential of honey is gradually growing and scientific evidence for the effectiveness of honey in several experimental and clinical conditions are beginning to emerge. Honey has been reported to be effective in gastrointestinal disorders [3], in the healing of wounds and burns [4], asthma [5], cataracts [6], cancer [7], and to provide gastric protection against acute and chronic gastric lesions [3].

Honey has also been shown to have antimicrobial, antiviral, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anticancer properties, in both in vitro and in vivo studies [8-10]. These properties are mainly attributed to the phenolic compounds in honey such as flavonoids which are recognized for their high pharmacological activities as antioxidant and radical scavengers [11,12].

Inflammation is a complex biological response of the body against infections, irritations or other injuries, cell damage and vascularized tissues and is critical for both innate and adaptive immunity [13,14]. Inflammation plays an important role in various diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis, asthma, inflammatory bowel disease, neurodegenerative diseases and cancer [15]. During an inflammatory response, several pro-inflammatory mediators are released, including interleukin 6 (IL-6), IL-12, tumour necrosis factor (TNF), interferon (INF- γ), cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) and inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) [16]. These cytokines play major roles in the initiation and amplification of inflammatory processes [17]. Nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B), transcription factor, also plays an important role in the inflammatory response by regulating the expression of various genes encoding pro-inflammatory mediators such as cytokines, chemokines, growth factors and inducible enzymes [18,19]. NF- κ B family consists of five proteins: NF- κ B1 (p50/p105), NF- κ B2 (p52/p100), RelA (p65), RelB and c-Rel [20]. It is found in the cytoplasm in an inactive form associated with regulatory proteins called inhibitors of κ B (I κ B) [21]. I κ B kinase (IKK) complex is a key kinase which phosphorylates the protein I κ B leading to proteasomal degradation of I κ B and activation of the NF- κ B [22]. Once activated, NF- κ B is translocated to the nucleus from the cytoplasm, which then activates the genes related to inflammatory responses [23].

Thus, inhibition of NF- κ B could reduce the expression of inflammatory genes and is a mechanism by which anti-inflammatory agents might elicit their anti-inflammatory effects [24].

Honey has been to exhibit anti-inflammatory activity through inactivation of NF- κ B via different mechanisms. For example, Hussein *et al.* [25] reported that the Gelam honey has anti-inflammatory effects by alleviating the rat paw edema and inhibiting the expression of pro-inflammatory mediators such as iNOS, COX-2, IL-6 and TNF- α in inflammation-induced paw edema in rats. Honey has been reported to have immunomodulatory activities of monocytic cells to repair the wounded tissue by releasing anti-inflammatory cytokines and growth factors [26,27]. Its effectiveness in rapidly clearing up the infection and promoting healing is not surprising in light of a large number of research findings on its antibacterial activity. It also possesses anti-inflammatory activity by inhibiting prostaglandins [28] and thrombin-induced oxidative burst in phagocytes [29]. Also, it has been reported that honey reduced the activities of cyclooxygenase-1 and cyclooxygenase-2, thus showing anti-inflammatory effects. Furthermore, ingestion of diluted natural honey has produced reductions on concentrations of prostaglandins such as PGE2 (prostaglandin E2), PGF2 α (prostaglandin F2a) and thromboxane B2 in plasma of normal individuals [18].

Pharmaceutical anti-inflammatory drugs are very widely used, but their use is limited by their having harmful side-effects. Honey has an anti-inflammatory action free from major side effects. This bioactivity of honey is far less well known than its antibacterial activity. Despite the foundation of many studies of the anti-inflammatory, antibacterial and antioxidant activities in honey types with different botanical origins, it appears that there are no data for the anti-inflammatory activities of Yemeni honey for the assessment of their quality and possible therapeutic potential. This study aimed to evaluate the anti-inflammatory activities of eight different types of Yemeni honey using an acute inflammation rat model.

Materials and methods

Honey samples

A total of eight samples of different floral Yemeni honey were directly obtained from the beekeepers living in the different regions of Yemen as apparent in Table 1 and Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Collected mono-floral honey types produced across Yemen

Table1. Honey samples and location

No	Honey types	Location
H1	Osaimi sider (<i>Ziziphus Spina-christi L.</i>)	Amran
H2	Athel (<i>Tamarix L.</i>)	Ibb
H3	Dam Al-Akhawain (<i>Dracaena cinnabari</i>)	Socotra
H4	Salam (<i>Acacia ehrenbergina</i>)	Tehamah
H5	Somar (<i>Acacia edgeworhi</i>)	Hadramout
H6	Majra (<i>Teucrium polium</i>)	Dhmar
H7	Acacia (<i>Acacia asak</i>)	Hajjah
H8	Algasas (<i>Euphorbia cactus Ehrenb</i>)	Damt-Adali

Animal Model and Experimental Design

Male albino rats 3-4 months old, weighing 280-320g were obtained from the zoo, Sana'a-Yemen. They were housed in stainless steel cages in a well-ventilated room at the Histological and Physiological Laboratories-Faculty of Medical Sciences, Queen Arwa University. The animals

were kept under controlled environmental conditions with free access to standard laboratory diet and water *ad libitum* during the entire period of the study 2017–2018. All animal experiments were carried out following the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals published by the National Institute of Health (NIH, 1978). The experimental protocols used in this study were approved by the Animal Ethics Committee of Zoo, Sana'a, Yemen.

Carrageenan-induced paw edema model was used for the assessment of anti-inflammatory activity [30], as described previously in Hussein *et al.* [31]. Briefly, ten groups were employed in this study (n=8 rats for each group). The groups from 2-9 represent rats that were pre-treated with different types of Yemeni honey (Osaimi sider, Athel, Al-Akhawain, Salam, Somar, Majra, Acacia, and Algasas), respectively. In all of the groups, rats were pre-treated orally with different types of honey once daily at a dose (5mg/kg of body weight) for 7 days. The negative control (group 1) received an equivalent volume of vehicle (distilled water) and the positive control group (group 10) received a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) Indomethacin (10mg/kg of body weight) [32]. One hour after the last day of administration of different types of honey, vehicle or Indomethacin, paw edema was induced by subplantar injection of 0.2ml/paw of 1% freshly prepared carrageenan suspension in normal saline into the right hind paw of each rat [33]. The diameter of the hind paw was measured for assessment of the edema size at 1, 2, 4, 6 and 24 hours. Twenty-four hours after carrageenan injection, blood samples were taken from the eye and divided into two parts. The first was maintained in EDTA bulb and plain tubes for hematological assay whereas, the second was centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 20 min, and the serum was separated for biochemical tests.

Biochemical assay

The serum of aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), total protein (T. protein), albumin levels were measured by spectrophotometry according to the standard protocol supplied by the Spinreact commercial kits.

Hematological Assay

Estimation of RBCs, Hb, WBCs, PCV and differential leucocytes count (Neutrophils, Lymphocyte, Monocyte, Basophils and Eosinophil) were measured using automated hematology system (Sysmex America, Inc. Model:XE-2100).

Statistical Analysis

The mean value of each parameter was computed considering data on eight rats in each group. Two-way analysis of variance was performed to test dose and durational effects of IC. The mean value of each parameter of different groups was compared using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Duncan's new multiple range test fixing a minimum significance level of $P < 0.05$. Student's t-test was used to compare mean values wherever there were only two groups. The Efficacies were obtained by calculating the difference between the edema size in the treated and the control and the values were transformed into a percentage using mean index using the formula:

$$(a-b)/a*100= \text{efficacy}$$

where: a Mean of the edema size in the control, b Mean of edema size in the treated rats.

Results

1.1. Effects of different types of Yemeni honey on edema size

The anti-inflammatory activity of different types of Yemeni honey on edema size in rats paw tissues was shown in Table (2) and Fig. (2). The rats supplemented with Dam Al-Akhawain honey (G4), Salam honey (G5), Somar honey (G6) and Acacia honey (G8) at a dose (5mg/kg b.w) for 7 days, there was no significant decrease on the edema size when compared to the control (carrageenan group) at the first hour, while there was significant decrease at the second, fourth, sixth and twenty-fourth hours. The rats supplemented with Osaimi sider honey (G2), Athel honey (G3), Majra honey (G7) and Algasas honey (G9), were significant decrease on the edema size when compared to the control (carrageenan group) at the first, second, fourth, sixth and twenty-fourth hours. Rats in group 10 (Indomethacin) showed a high decrease ($p < 0.05$) in edema size when compared to the control (untreated group) at the first, second, fourth, sixth and twenty-fourth hours. Interestingly, the treatment with Majra honey (G7) and Algasas honey (G9) had a greater effect on edema size which was almost similar to the effect of the Indomethacin (10 mg/kg of body weight).

Table 2. Anti-inflammatory activity of different types of Yemeni honey carrageenan-induced paw edema in rats

Groups	Edema size (mm)									
	1 hr		2 hr		4 hr		6 hr		24 hr	
	M±SD	%								
G1	2.17±0.22 ^a	2.11±0.18 ^a	2.06±0.18 ^a	1.22±0.10 ^a	0.76±0.09 ^a
G2	2.02±0.18 ^b	5.53	1.71±0.21 ^b	18.96	1.63±0.16 ^b	20.87	0.81±0.08 ^b	33.61	0.29±0.10 ^b	61.84
G3	2.03±0.19 ^b	6.45	1.69±0.18 ^b	19.91	1.61±0.17 ^b	21.84	0.78±0.04 ^b	36.07	0.27±0.05 ^b	64.47
G4	2.11±0.17 ^a	2.76	1.68±0.17 ^b	20.38	1.6±0.16 ^b	22.33	0.83±0.07 ^b	31.97	0.3±0.04 ^b	60.53
G5	2.13±0.26 ^a	1.84	1.74±0.21 ^b	17.54	1.68±0.15 ^b	18.45	0.88±0.05 ^b	27.87	0.33±0.07 ^b	56.58
G6	2.13±0.28 ^a	1.84	1.72±0.22 ^b	18.48	1.67±0.18 ^b	18.93	0.86±0.04 ^b	29.51	0.34±0.06 ^b	55.26
G7	1.91±0.21 ^b	11.98	1.57±0.21 ^b	25.59	1.51±0.17 ^b	26.70	0.34±0.06 ^c	72.13	0.23±0.05 ^b	69.741
G8	2.11±0.20 ^a	2.76	1.68±0.19 ^b	20.38	1.61±0.18 ^b	21.84	0.77±0.06 ^b	36.89	0.29±0.08 ^b	61.84
G9	1.95±0.22 ^b	10.13	1.61±0.19 ^b	23.70	1.54±0.16 ^b	25.24	0.39±0.05 ^c	68.03	0.28±0.07 ^b	63.16
G10	1.54±0.29 ^b	29.03	1.45±0.19 ^b	31.28	1.5±0.14 ^b	27.18	0.24±0.03 ^c	80.32	0.19±0.07 ^b	75

Values are expressed M±S.E. of 8 rats, values with same superscript letters are not significantly different whereas those with different superscript letters are significantly ($P < 0.05$) different as judged by ANOVA followed by Duncan's multiple range test.

G1=(D.w + Carrageenan), G2=(5mg/kg Osaimi sider honey + Carrageenan), G3=(5mg/kg Athel honey + Carrageenan), G4=(5mg/kg Dam Al-Akhawain honey + Carrageenan), G5=(5mg/kg Salam honey + Carrageenan), G6=(5mg/kg Somar honey + Carrageenan), G7=(5mg/kg Majra honey + Carrageenan), G8=(5mg/kg Acacia honey + Carrageenan), G9=(5mg/kg Algasas honey + Carrageenan), G10=(10mg/kg Indomethacin + Carrageenan).

Figure 2. Vertical bars showing comparison of edema size in rats dosed with different types of Yemeni honey (M±SE. of eight rats). Bars with same superscript letters are not significantly different whereas those with different superscript letters are significantly ($p < 0.05$) different as judged by ANOVA followed by Duncan's multiple range test. G1=(D.w + Carrageenan), G2=(5mg/kg Osaimi sider honey + Carrageenan), G3=(5mg/kg Athel honey + Carrageenan), G4=(5mg/kg Dam Al-Akhawain honey + Carrageenan), G5=(5mg/kg Salam honey + Carrageenan), G6=(5mg/kg Somar honey + Carrageenan), G7=(5mg/kg Majra honey + Carrageenan), G8=(5mg/kg Acacia honey + Carrageenan), G9=(5mg/kg Algasas honey + Carrageenan), G10=(10 mg/kg Indomethacin + Carrageenan).

1.2. Effects of different types of Yemeni honey on hematological parameters

The results demonstrated that carrageenan injection induced the hematological values to change in the blood, as shown in Figures 3. However, the numbers of RBCs, levels of Hb and PCV increased significantly by the treatment with different types of Yemeni honey when compared to the control (carrageenan group) together with a significant reduction in WBCs numbers when

compared to the control (carrageenan group). Rats in group 10 (Indomethacin) showed a high increase ($p < 0.05$) in numbers of RBCs, levels of Hb and PCV together with a significant reduction in WBCs numbers when compared to the control (carrageenan group). The treatment with Majra honey (G7) and Algasas honey (G9) had a greater effect on hematological values in blood followed Dam Al-Akhawain honey (G4) and Osaimi sider honey (G2) which were almost similar to the effect of the Indomethacin (10 mg/kg of body weight).

Figure 3. Vertical bars showing Average (mean \pm SE) Hematological values of rats treated with different types of Yemeni honey and Indomethacin (M \pm SE. of eight rats). Bars with same superscript letters are not significantly different whereas those with different superscript letters are significantly ($p < 0.05$) different as judged by ANOVA followed by Duncan's multiple range test. G1=(D.w + Carrageenan), G2=(5mg/kg Osaimi sider honey + Carrageenan), G3=(5mg/kg Athel honey + Carrageenan), G4=(5mg/kg Dam Al-Akhawain honey + Carrageenan), G5=(5mg/kg Salam honey + Carrageenan), G6=(5mg/kg Somar honey + Carrageenan), G7=(5mg/kg Majra honey + Carrageenan), G8=(5mg/kg Acacia honey + Carrageenan), G9=(5mg/kg Algasas honey + Carrageenan), G10=(10 mg/kg Indomethacin + Carrageenan).

1.3. Effects of different types of Yemeni honey on leucocytes count

Figure (4) summarizes the changes in leucocytes count; neutrophil, lymphocyte, monocyte, basophils and eosinophil percentages of rats treated with different types of Yemeni honey and Indomethacin.

Fig. 4. Vertical bars showing Average (mean \pm SE) values of leucocytes count of rats treated with different types of Yemeni honey and Indomethacin (M \pm SE. of eight rats). Bars with same superscript letters are not significantly different whereas those with different superscript letters are significantly ($p < 0.05$) different as judged by ANOVA followed by Duncan's multiple range test. G1=(D.w

+ Carrageenan), G2=(5mg/kg Osaimi sider honey + Carrageenan), G3=(5mg/kg Athel honey + Carrageenan), G4=(5mg/kg Dam Al-Akhawain honey + Carrageenan), G5=(5mg/kg Salam honey + Carrageenan), G6=(5mg/kg Somar honey + Carrageenan), G7=(5mg/kg Majra honey + Carrageenan), G8=(5mg/kg Acacia honey + Carrageenan), G9=(5mg/kg Algasas honey + Carrageenan), G10=(10 mg/kg Indomethacin + Carrageenan).

All types of honey and Indomethacin showed no significant differences in monocytes and eosinophil percentage when compared to the (carrageenan group), while there was significant ($p<0.05$) increase in neutrophils, lymphocyte and basophils percentage when compared to the (carrageenan group). Interestingly, the treatment with Majra honey (G7) and Algasas honey (G9) had a greater effect on leucocytes count in blood followed Dam Al-Akhawain honey (G4), Osaimi sider honey (G2) and Acacia honey (G8) which were almost similar to the effect of the Indomethacin (10 mg/kg of body weight).

1.4. Effects of different types of Yemeni honey on serum metabolites

Figure (5) summarized the change in serum metabolites of rats treated with different types of Yemeni honey and Indomethacin. In all treated groups there were no significant changes in levels of total protein and albumin and no significant change in the activity of ALT when compared to the control (carrageenan group). The rats treated with Salam honey (G5), Somar honey (G6) and Acacia honey (G8), caused no significant increase on the activity of AST when compared to the control (carrageenan group), while showed significant increase in the activity of ALT in rats that treated with Osaimi sider honey (G2), Athel honey (G3), Dam Al-Akhawain honey (G4) Majra honey (G7) and Algasas honey (G9) when compared to the control (carrageenan group). Rats in group 10 (Indomethacin) showed no significant changes in levels of total protein, albumin and activity of ALT when compared to the control (carrageenan group), while showed a significant increase in the activity of AST when compared to the control.

Fig. 5. Vertical bars showing Average (mean \pm SE) values of serum metabolites of rats treated with different types of Yemeni honey and Indomethacin ($M \pm SE$. of eight rats). Bars with same superscript letters are not significantly different whereas those with different superscript letters are significantly ($p < 0.05$) different as judged by ANOVA followed by Duncan's multiple range test. G1=(D.w + Carrageenan), G2=(5mg/kg Osaimi sider honey + Carrageenan), G3=(5mg/kg Athel honey + Carrageenan), G4=(5mg/kg Dam Al-Akhawain honey + Carrageenan), G5=(5mg/kg Salam honey + Carrageenan), G6=(5mg/kg Somar honey + Carrageenan), G7=(5mg/kg Majra honey + Carrageenan), G8=(5mg/kg Acacia honey + Carrageenan), G9=(5mg/kg Algasas honey + Carrageenan), G10=(10 mg/kg Indomethacin + Carrageenan).

Discussion

Inflammation is part of the host defense mechanism against infectious agents and injury and it is also involved in the pathophysiology of many diseases when left unresolved. Acute inflammation is a short-term process which is characterized by typical signs of inflammation, such as swelling, redness, heat, pain and loss of function due to the infiltration of the tissues by leukocytes and plasma [34,35].

The present results showed that Carrageenan injection induced a significant increase in edema size in rats paw tissues. Carrageenan induced-edema has been commonly used in experimental

animal models for inducing acute inflammation Hajare et al. [36] Hussein et al. [25] Kareem [37]. Inflammation is believed to be biphasic, the early phase (1–2 h) of the carrageenan model is mainly mediated by histamine, serotonin and increased synthesis of prostaglandins in the damage tissue surroundings and the late phase is sustained by prostaglandins release and mediated by leukotrienes, bradykinin, polymorphonuclear cells and prostaglandins produced by tissue macrophages [38-41].

Also, many studies reported that Indomethacin is a standard anti-inflammatory drug in inhibiting response induced by various inflammagens in an acute model of inflammation [42,43] (*Claria and Romano, 2005, Osman, 2005*). The reduction in the size of the induced edema indicates the anti-inflammatory activity of the honey. The findings of this study confirmed that the Dam Al-Akhawain honey, Salam honey, Somar honey and Acacia honey showed significant inhibition of edema size at the second, fourth, sixth and twenty-fourth hours of treatment, while Osaimi sider honey, Athel honey, Majra honey and Algasas honey showed significant inhibition of edema size at the first, second, fourth, sixth and twenty-fourth hours of treatment. Interestingly, the treatment with Majra honey and Algasas honey had a greater effect on edema size which was almost similar to the effect of the Indomethacin, this study agrees with Kareem [37] who studies the anti-inflammatory activity of *Ziziphus spina christi* leaves and with Hussein et al. [25] who studies the anti-inflammatory activity of Gelam honey. Hussein et al. [31] showed that the anti-inflammatory properties of honey it reduces edema in a dose dependent fashion in inflamed rat paw with concomitant reduced production of pro-inflammatory mediators (both genes and proteins) such as iNOS, COX-2, IL-6 and TNF- α in plasma and tissues [25,37]. In addition, Hussein et al. [11,31]; Al-Mamary et al. [44] reported that honey contains many phenolic compounds such as ellagic acid, gallic acid, caffeic acid, quercetin and chrysin, which correlated to its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities. It is well known that some honey constituents like flavonoids and total phenolics, can significantly inhibit the biosynthetic pathway of these mediators such as prostaglandins, histamine, serotonin and bradykinin [45]. Besides, as was mentioned flavonoids and terpenoids had been reported to have anti-inflammatory effects. A number of previous studies suggested that flavonoids may interact directly with the prostaglandins system in the same way as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs [46,47]. Among the above facts, flavonoids can be responsible for the anti-inflammatory effects of different types of Yemeni honey in this study.

The present studies established that the anti-inflammatory activity of the different types of Yemeni honey. Some biochemical assay was recorded including ALT, total protein and albumin and also hematological parameters like Hb, PCV and RBC count reveals no toxicity evidence of the doses used and so indicate effectiveness and safety activities for the treatment of conditions associated with inflammation. The significant increase in AST activity in carrageenan group indicates tissue damage and a significant decrease in AST and ALT activities in honey groups and Indomethacin group can be pointed out as another evidence of anti-inflammatory activity of the honey. Also, in the present study, the result obtained in the leucocytes count showed that different types of Yemeni honey significantly reduced the values of leucocytes count, suggesting that the active principles present in the honey may act as an anti-inflammatory. Neutrophils participate in the endogenous control of the inflammatory pain in rats [48]. In different types of Yemeni honey, a significant decrease in lymphocyte, basophils and neutrophil percentage may be due to anti-inflammatory activity of honey. Whereas the carrageenan group recorded a higher percentage of neutrophils, basophils and lymphocytes and a higher count of white blood cells. This was explained in the study of [49] that the animal body may point out some chemical and their metabolite as invading hemotoxicants. No change in monocytes and eosinophil count (eosinophil share in parasitic inflammation and monocytes share in viral inflammation). Hussein et al. [25] they evaluated the mechanism by which honey exerts its anti-inflammatory effect in association with NF- κ B signalling pathway by evaluating the genes and proteins that are involved in the pathway. The findings of the study confirmed the nuclear translocation of NF- κ B subunits (p65 and p50) and cytoplasmic degradation of I κ B α during inflammation as induced in rats by carrageenan injection. However, pre-treatment with Gelam honey significantly inhibited the nuclear translocation of NF κ B subunits (p65 and p50) as supported by increased levels of p65 and p50 protein in the cytosol and decreased cytosolic I κ B α degradation. Various in vitro and in vivo experimental studies have reported the inhibitory effects of several natural products and polyphenols on the production of pro-inflammatory mediators through attenuating the activation of NF- κ B pathway. In addition, it has been reported that honey reduced the activities of cyclooxygenase-1 and cyclooxygenase-2, thus showing anti-inflammatory effects. Furthermore, ingestion of diluted natural honey has produced reductions on concentrations of prostaglandins such as PGE₂ (prostaglandin E₂), PGF₂ α (prostaglandin F_{2a}) and thromboxane B₂ in plasma of normal individuals [18]. Interestingly, in an inflammatory model of colitis, honey was as effective

as prednisolone treatment [19]. While NSAIDS and corticosteroids may have many serious side effects, honey has an anti-inflammatory action free from major side effects. Recently, Gelam honey has been demonstrated to decrease inflammatory mediators such as COX-2 and TNF- α via attenuating NF- κ B translocation to the nucleus and thus inhibiting the activation of the NF- κ B pathway [50]. It is widely known that the activation of NF- κ B plays a key role in the pathogenesis of inflammation [51,52]. Therefore, Gelam honey has just been documented to inhibit the inflammatory process by inhibiting NF- κ B pathway.

Conclusion

The different types of Yemeni honey (Osaimi sider, Athel, Dam Al-Akhawain, Salam, Somar, Majra, Acacia and Algasas) possess anti-inflammatory activity. Also, they were safe at the doses used. The Majra honey, Algasas honey and Osaimi sider honey possess a better anti-inflammatory activity, which were almost similar to the effect of the Indomethacin, followed Dam Al-Akhawain honey and Acacia honey, then Athel honey, Salam honey and Somar honey, where their anti-inflammatory activity differed according to the source and the level of honey. Therefore, these discrepancies could be attributed to the differences of botanical sources of honey and also to the presence of different compounds of anti-inflammatory that have different anti-inflammation effects. Hence, further studies on the chemical, biochemical properties, and anti-inflammatory capabilities of the monofloral honey types produced in Yemen.

References

1. ALVAREZ-SUAREZ, J. M., TULIPANI, S., DÍAZ, D., ESTEVEZ, Y., ROMANDINI, S., GIAMPIERI, F., DAMIANI, E., ASTOLFI, P., BOMPADRE, S. & BATTINO, M. 2010. Antioxidant and antimicrobial capacity of several monofloral Cuban honeys and their correlation with color, polyphenol content and other chemical compounds. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 48, 2490-2499.
2. BLASA, M., CANDIRACCI, M., ACCORSI, A., PIACENTINI, M. P., ALBERTINI, M. C. & PIATTI, E. 2006. Raw Millefiori honey is packed full of antioxidants. *Food Chemistry*, 97, 217-222.

3. ALI, A. T. M. M. & AL SWAYEH, O. A. 2003. Honey potentiates the gastric protection effects of sucralfate against ammonia-induced gastric lesions in rats. *Saudi Journal of Gastroenterology*, 9, 117.
4. AL-WAILI, N., SALOM, K. & AL-GHAMDI, A. A. 2011. Honey for wound healing, ulcers, and burns; data supporting its use in clinical practice. *The scientific world journal*, 11, 766-787.
5. ORHAN, F., SEKEREL, B. E., KOCABAS, C. N., SACKESEN, C., ADALIOGLU, G. & TUNCER, A. 2003. Complementary and alternative medicine in children with asthma. *Annals of Allergy, Asthma & Immunology*, 90, 611-615.
6. PATRICIA, V. 2002. Effect of stingless bee honey in selenite induced cataracts. *Apiacta*, 3, 1-2.
7. SWELLAM, T., MIYANAGA, N., ONOZAWA, M., HATTORI, K., KAWAI, K., SHIMAZUI, T. & AKAZA, H. 2003. Antineoplastic activity of honey in an experimental bladder cancer implantation model: in vivo and in vitro studies. *International journal of urology*, 10, 213-219.
8. ESTEVINHO, L., PEREIRA, A. P., MOREIRA, L., DIAS, L. G. & PEREIRA, E. 2008. Antioxidant and antimicrobial effects of phenolic compounds extracts of Northeast Portugal honey. *Food and chemical toxicology*, 46, 3774-3779.
9. FAUZI, A. N., NORAZMI, M. N. & YAACOB, N. S. 2011. Tualang honey induces apoptosis and disrupts the mitochondrial membrane potential of human breast and cervical cancer cell lines. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 49, 871-878.
10. OWOYELE, B. V., ADENEKAN, O. T. & SOLADOYE, A. O. 2011. Effects of honey on inflammation and nitric oxide production in Wistar rats. *Zhong Xi Yi Jie He Xue Bao*, 9, 447-452.
11. HUSSEIN, S. Z., YUSOFF, K. M., MAKPOL, S. & YUSOF, Y. A. M. 2011. Antioxidant capacities and total phenolic contents increase with gamma irradiation in two types of Malaysian honey. *Molecules*, 16, 6378-6395.
12. YAO, L. H., JIANG, Y. M., SHI, J., TOMAS-BARBERAN, F. A., DATTA, N., SINGANUSONG, R. & CHEN, S. S. 2004. Flavonoids in food and their health benefits. *Plant foods for human nutrition*, 59, 113-122.

13. FERRERO-MILIANI, L., NIELSEN, O. H., ANDERSEN, P. S. & GIRARDIN, S. E. 2007. Chronic inflammation: importance of NOD2 and NALP3 in interleukin-1 β generation. *Clinical & Experimental Immunology*, 147, 227-235.
14. LAWRENCE, T. & FONG, C. 2010. The resolution of inflammation: anti-inflammatory roles for NF- κ B. *The international journal of biochemistry & cell biology*, 42, 519-523.
15. IWALEWA, E. O., MCGAW, L. J., NAIDOO, V. & ELOFF, J. N. 2007. Inflammation: the foundation of diseases and disorders. A review of phytomedicines of South African origin used to treat pain and inflammatory conditions. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 6.
16. HUNG, T. M., DANG, N. H., KIM, J. C., CHOI, J. S., LEE, H. K. & MIN, B.-S. 2009. Phenolic glycosides from *Alangium salviifolium* leaves with inhibitory activity on LPS-induced NO, PGE₂, and TNF- α production. *Bioorganic & medicinal chemistry letters*, 19, 4389-4393.
17. CALIXTO, J. B., CAMPOS, M. M., OTUKI, M. F. & SANTOS, A. R. S. 2004. Anti-inflammatory compounds of plant origin. Part II. Modulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines, chemokines and adhesion molecules. *Planta medica*, 70, 93-103.
18. REYES-GORDILLO, K., SEGOVIA, J., SHIBAYAMA, M., VERGARA, P., MORENO, M. G. & MURIEL, P. 2007. Curcumin protects against acute liver damage in the rat by inhibiting NF- κ B, proinflammatory cytokines production and oxidative stress. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-General Subjects*, 1770, 989-996.
19. HIMAYA, S. W. A., RYU, B., QIAN, Z.-J., LI, Y. & KIM, S.-K. 2011. 1-(5-bromo-2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl) ethanone [SE1] suppresses pro-inflammatory responses by blocking NF- κ B and MAPK signaling pathways in activated microglia. *European journal of pharmacology*, 670, 608-616.
20. LEE, C. H., JEON, Y. T., KIM, S. H. & SONG, Y. S. 2007. NF- κ B as a potential molecular target for cancer therapy. *Biofactors*, 29, 19-35.
21. TAK, P. P. & FIRESTEIN, G. S. 2001. NF- κ B: a key role in inflammatory diseases. *The Journal of clinical investigation*, 107, 7-11.
22. OH, B. K., MUN, J., SEO, H. W., RYU, S. Y., KIM, Y. S., LEE, B. H. & OH, K.-S. 2011. *Euonymus alatus* extract attenuates LPS-induced NF- κ B activation via IKK β inhibition in RAW 264.7 cells. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, 134, 288-293.
23. BALDWIN, A. S. 2001. Series introduction: the transcription factor NF- κ B and human disease. *The Journal of clinical investigation*, 107, 3-6.

24. KANG, O.-H., JANG, H.-J., CHAE, H.-S., OH, Y.-C., CHOI, J.-G., LEE, Y.-S., KIM, J.-H., KIM, Y. C., SOHN, D. H. & PARK, H. 2009. Anti-inflammatory mechanisms of resveratrol in activated HMC-1 cells: pivotal roles of NF- κ B and MAPK. *Pharmacological research*, 59, 330-337.
25. HUSSEIN, S. Z., MOHD YUSOFF, K., MAKPOL, S. & MOHD YUSOF, Y. A. 2013. Gelam Honey Attenuates Carrageenan-Induced Rat Paw Inflammation via NF- κ B.
26. HENRIQUES, A., JACKSON, S., COOPER, R. & BURTON, N. 2006. Free radical production and quenching in honeys with wound healing potential. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*, 58, 773-777.
27. TONKS, A. J., COOPER, R. A., JONES, K. P., BLAIR, S., PARTON, J. & TONKS, A. 2003. Honey stimulates inflammatory cytokine production from monocytes. *Cytokine*, 21, 242-247.
28. AL-WAILI, N. S. & BONI, N. S. 2003. Natural honey lowers plasma prostaglandin concentrations in normal individuals. *Journal of medicinal food*, 6, 129-133.
29. AHMAD, A., KHAN, R. A. & MESAİK, M. A. 2009. Anti inflammatory effect of natural honey on bovine thrombin-induced oxidative burst in phagocytes. *Phytotherapy Research: An International Journal Devoted to Pharmacological and Toxicological Evaluation of Natural Product Derivatives*, 23, 801-808.
30. WINTER, G. A., RISLEY, E. & NUSS, G. 1962. Risley, EA. and Nuss, GW.(1962). Carrageenan-induced oedema in hind paw of the rat as an assay for anti-inflammatory drugs. *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med*, 3, 544-547
31. HUSSEIN, S. Z., MOHD YUSOFF, K., MAKPOL, S., YUSOF, M. & ANUM, Y. 2012. Gelam honey inhibits the production of proinflammatory, mediators NO, PGE₂, TNF- α , and IL-6 in carrageenan-induced acute paw edema in rats. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2012.
32. IGBE, I., CHING, F. P. & EROMON, A. 2010. Anti-inflammatory activity of aqueous fruit pulp extract of *Hunteria umbellata* K. Schum in acute and chronic inflammation. *Acta Pol Pharm*, 67, 81-85.
33. KASSIM, M., ACHOUI, M., MANSOR, M. & YUSOFF, K. M. 2010. The inhibitory effects of Gelam honey and its extracts on nitric oxide and prostaglandin E₂ in inflammatory tissues. *Fitoterapia*, 81, 1196-1201.

34. LIBBY, P. 2007. Inflammatory mechanisms: the molecular basis of inflammation and disease. *Nutrition reviews*, 65, S140-S146.
35. GYURKOVSKA, V., ALIPIEVA, K., MACIUK, A., DIMITROVA, P., IVANOVSKA, N., HAAS, C., BLEY, T. & GEORGIEV, M. 2011. Anti-inflammatory activity of Devil's claw in vitro systems and their active constituents. *Food Chemistry*, 125, 171-178.
36. HAJARE, S. W., CHANDRA, S., SHARMA, J., TANDAN, S. K., LAL, J. & TELANG, A. G. 2001. Anti-inflammatory activity of Dalbergia sissoo leaves. *Fitoterapia*, 72, 131-139.
37. KAREEM, M. A. A. A. 2008. Anti-inflammatory Activity of Trigonella foenum grecum and Ziziphus spina christi on Rats.
38. POSADAS, I., BUCCI, M., ROVIEZZO, F., ROSSI, A., PARENTE, L., SAUTEBIN, L. & CIRINO, G. 2004. Carrageenan-induced mouse paw oedema is biphasic, age-weight dependent and displays differential nitric oxide cyclooxygenase-2 expression. *British journal of pharmacology*, 142, 331-338.
39. BADILLA, B., ARIAS, A. Y., ARIAS, M., MORA, G. A. & POVEDA, L. J. 2003. Anti-inflammatory and antinociceptive activities of Loasa speciosa in rats and mice. *Fitoterapia*, 74, 45-51.
40. GUPTA, M., MAZUMDER, U. K., GOMATHI, P. & SELVAN, V. T. 2006. Antiinflammatory evaluation of leaves of Plumeria acuminata. *BMC Complementary and alternative medicine*, 6, 1-6.
41. ANTONIO, M. A. & BRITO, A. R. M. S. 1998. Oral anti-inflammatory and anti-ulcerogenic activities of a hydroalcoholic extract and partitioned fractions of Turnera ulmifolia (Turneraceae). *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, 61, 215-228.
42. CLARIA, J. & ROMANO, M. 2005. Pharmacological intervention of cyclooxygenase-2 and 5-lipoxygenase pathways. Impact on inflammation and cancer. *Current pharmaceutical design*, 11, 3431-3447.
43. OSMAN, O. A. 2005. Studies on Neem (Azadirachta indica) Seed Toxicity to rats and chicks.
44. AL-MAMARY, M., AL-MEERI, A. & AL-HABORI, M. 2002. Antioxidant activities and total phenolics of different types of honey. *Nutrition research*, 22, 1041-1047.
45. VALLIANOU, N. G., GOUNARI, P., SKOURTIS, A., PANAGOS, J. & KAZAZIS, C. 2014. Honey and its anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial and anti-oxidant properties. *Gen Med (Los Angel)*, 2, 1-5.

46. PANTHONG, A., TASSANEYAKUL, W., KANJANAPOTHI, D., TANTIWACHWUTTIKUL, P. & REUTRAKUL, V. 1989. Anti-inflammatory activity of 5, 7-dimethoxyflavone. *Planta medica*, 55, 133-136.
47. DEL CARMEN RECIO, M., GINER, R. M., MANEZ, S., TALENS, A., CUBELLS, L., GUEHO, J., JULIEN, H. R., HOSTETTMANN, K. & RIOS, J. L. 1995. Anti-inflammatory activity of flavonol glycosides from *Erythrospermum monticolum* depending on single or repeated local TPA administration. *Planta medica*, 61, 502-504.
48. GIORGI, R., PAGANO, R. L., DIAS, M. A. A., AGUIAR-PASSETI, T., SORG, C. & MARIANO, M. 1998. Antinociceptive effect of the calcium-binding protein MRP-14 and the role played by neutrophils on the control of inflammatory pain. *Journal of leukocyte biology*, 64, 214-220.
49. WEBER, C. I. 1991. *Methods for measuring the acute toxicity of effluents and receiving waters to freshwater and marine organisms*, Environmental Monitoring Systems Laboratory, Office of Research.
50. AL-WAILI, N. S. 2004. Natural honey lowers plasma glucose, C-reactive protein, homocysteine, and blood lipids in healthy, diabetic, and hyperlipidemic subjects: comparison with dextrose and sucrose. *Journal of Medicinal Food*, 7, 100-107.
51. JOHNSTON, J. E., SEPE, H. A., MIANO, C. L., BRANNAN, R. G. & ALDERTON, A. L. 2005. Honey inhibits lipid oxidation in ready-to-eat ground beef patties. *Meat science*, 70, 627-631.
52. TURKMEN, N., SARI, F., POYRAZOGLU, E. S. & VELIOGLU, Y. S. 2006. Effects of prolonged heating on antioxidant activity and colour of honey. *Food Chemistry*, 95, 653-657.

Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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